

Documenting Also Means Publishing:

On the Responsible Handling of Observations on iNaturalist

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Introduction

This is a question I encounter time and again: Should one actually publish their observations? The discussion is justified, because there are both opportunities and risks. Here I want to present both sides – critically and constructively – and finally state my own position. For me it is clear: responsible publication is a gain for nature, society, and science.

Critical voices

- Disclosure of sensitive locations: can endanger rare species – through collection, illegal keeping, or targeted specific overtourism.
- Disturbance of habitats: may occur when too many people deliberately visit sensitive sites.

- Data protection and personal safety: Even “ordinary” species should sometimes be entered as obscured when they occur temporally or spatially close to sensitive species – otherwise conclusions can be drawn.
- Regional differences in species protection: Along the Nahe River, dice snakes are actively highlighted; signs advise cyclists to dismount and walk their bikes to avoid harming the snakes. In Baden-Württemberg, by contrast, the habitats of the Asp viper in the southern Black Forest are deliberately kept secret. Both concepts are justified, as they reflect the specific conditions and requirements of their respective regions.
- Data quality: Some question the robustness of citizen-science data, since not all observations are verified by experts.

Positive Aspekte

- Scientific data basis: Every observation is a building block for biodiversity research.
- Conservation through knowledge: Species can only be protected if their occurrences are known.
- Transparency and awareness: iNaturalist makes biodiversity visible and brings it into public discourse.
- Citizen science: Observers become part of a global community and actively contribute to science.
- Positive examples: Public information about Aesculapian snakes and dice snakes promotes protection, acceptance, and understanding.

Lösungen für die Praxis

- Location obscuration: for sensitive species – and sometimes also for “ordinary” species when they occur directly alongside sensitive ones.
- Delayed publication: to prevent immediate conclusions.
- Selective data release: not every observation must be public.
- Community awareness: understanding and applying responsible data entry.

Mein Votum

The advantages outweigh the risks. Without data, species remain invisible – and invisible species are almost impossible to protect. Observations should be published – responsibly, thoughtfully, and with the available protective mechanisms.

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